

hills died. The 2 photoperiod-sensitive varieties flowered 120 d after the main crop harvest. Fertilized ratoon crops of the tall varieties partially lodged.

The photoperiod-sensitive varieties yielded appreciably lower in the main crop than the two high-yielding varieties (see table) because the number of mature panicles was much lower. In the ratoon crop, IR30 and IR50 yields were appreciably lower than their main crop yields. CR1014 and Kumragore also had reduced ratoon yields, but not as much.

Panicles per unit area, grains per panicle, and grain test weight in IR50 and IR36 were lower in the ratoon crop than in the main crop. Except in test weight, reductions were not significant in the CR1014 and Kumragore ratoons. Residual P effect was not significant in the ratoon crops.

IR50 can be ratooned to produce a total yield of 7 t/ha. □

Effect of fertilizer treatment on growth and productivity of main and ratoon crops in West Bengal.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles /m ²	Grains/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Duration (d)
<i>Main crop</i>					
N 100	3.2	251	74	19.90	
NP 100-22	3.8	313	85	20.6	
NK 100-42	3.3	244	76	20.0	
NPK 100-22-42	3.9	327	91	20.6	
CD at 5%	0.4	49	8	0.3	
IR50	5.3	417	89	21.7	153
IR36	5.1	399	83	20.9	153
CR1014	1.6	197	90	15.0	173
Kumragore	2.2	284	84	23.5	173
CD at 5%	0.2	38	6.2	0.5	
<i>Ratoon crop</i>					
N 100	1.5	272	62	18.5	
NP 100-22	1.8	325	76	19.4	
NK 100-42	1.6	278	66	18.6	
NPK 100-22-42	1.8	319	74	19.0	
CD at 5%	0.1	ns	ns	ns	
IR50	1.7	312	51	18.6	90 ^a
IR36	1.4	302	49	18.4	90 ^a
CR1014	1.7	292	91	16.0	170
Kumragore	1.7	288	87	22.5	170
CD at 5%	0.1	ns	10	0.7	

^aStarted flowering 30 days after main crop harvest.

Effect of shallow submergence on agronomic characters

M.S. Rao, Agricultural Research Station (ARS), Pulla, West Godavari District; and P.S.S. Murthy, ARS, Maruteru, West Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India

We studied the effect of shallow submergence on four popular rices and two tall varieties. Entries received shallow submergence (60 cm) for 70 d starting from 40 d after transplanting.

Water level in the control plots was 5-7.5 cm. Performance in shallow submergence was evaluated by grain yield and other agronomic characters.

Shallow submergence resulted in an increase in plant height (32%) and flowering duration (3%), and a decrease in panicle-bearing tillers (30%), total spikelets (12%), and filled grains (19%) (see table). This resulted in a 50% decrease in grain yield.

Under submergence, CN540 had the highest yield (3.1 t/ha), followed by PLA1100 (2.7 t/ha). □

Complete slide sets of photos printed in Field problems of tropical rice, revised 1983, are available for purchase at \$50 (less developed country price) or \$60 (developed country price), including airmail postage and handling, from the Communication and Publications Department, Division R, IRRI, P. O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines. No orders for surface mail handling will be accepted.

Grain yield and other agronomic characteristics of rice varieties in shallow submergence. Pulla, Andhra Pradesh, India, 1984 kharif.

Variety	Parentage	Plant ht (cm) at maturity		Flowering duration (d)		Panicle-bearing tillers/plant		Total spikelets/panicle		Fertility (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
		Control	60 cm water	Control	60 cm water	Control	60 cm water	Control	60 cm water	Control	60 cm water	Control	60 cm water
MTU5182	MTU4569/ARC6650	108	146	131	134	11	7	202	198	98	96	5.4	2.4
MTU5293	MTU4569/ARC6650	104	145	141	144	11	7	178	146	60	68	5.3	2.4
MTU4870	MTU4569/ARC6650	109	155	135	142	9	6	165	153	99	80	5.1	1.4
PLA1100	Mahsuri/Vijaya	94	136	140	148	10	8	280	235	91	69	5.5	2.7
CN540	IR262/Khao Nahng Nuey 11	141	181	130	130	9	7	236	222	93	89	5.0	3.1
NC492	Pureline selection	178	203	140	140	8	7	183	135	78	81	4.8	2.6
Mean		122	161	136	140	10	7	207	182	86	80	5.2	2.4